

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D6.10 National Focal Points projects

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¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
 OTHER=Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Use one of the following codes: PU=Public, fully open, e.g. web
 CO=Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
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1 Introduction and Objectives

The work-package 6 of ANIMA project deals with the global coordination of aviation noise in Europe. The EU project Xnoise, aiming at network coordination and scientific exchanges, was initiated in the 2000's and run until 2016 (Xnoise-EV). A part of the network activities was included in ANIMA and concerns mainly two parts:

- the Common Strategic Research Roadmap for aviation noise reduction (Task 6.1),
- the European Aviation Noise network (Task 6.2).

In this framework, ANIMA managed regular scientific workshops through which the research community reported the advancement of scientific and technological developments related to aviation noise. The present deliverable was supposed to give account for the third of such workshops. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 crisis pushed the consortium to postpone twice and finally to cancel this third workshop. As a kind of compensation, the consortium proposed to report in this deliverable on the National efforts that ANIMA helped to consolidate through regular report of the European Network of Noise Experts it succeeded to manage despite the crisis.

This report therefore addresses the Tasks 6.2.3 and 6.2.4 concerning the network consolidation and extension with a special attention to Eastern EU countries participation and the regular animation for an active network functioning including the promotion of the research efforts.

In the frame of the Task 6.2.3 an important action was engaged to identify the National Efforts of each country (national actions additional to EU projects) for the aviation noise mitigation.

The main goals targeted are:

- identify and collect the national efforts, **additional to EU projects**, in terms of research actions, scientific and technical activities dealing with aircraft noise reduction
- share national information at European level for a better coordination,
- contribute to a common strategic research roadmap for aviation noise reduction.

Despite the COVID-19 crisis, the objectives are fully reached thanks to the fruitful contributions of all the participants.

2 NFP network

The aviation noise network was created in the frame of the first Xnoise project (1998-2001) funded by EU. Since two decades, the network has gained good practices and experience in formal relationships between the partners. For an efficient functioning of a wide network, a key objective was obtain a complete list the national focal points representing each country and to update it regularly.

The main objectives of ANIMA/WP6 were to maintain the dynamics of the existing Xnoise networking efforts and to gather in the aviation noise community the

involvement of new experts. A special action was to extend the network, as wide as possible, focusing on central and east European countries not involved previously in Xnoise.

At the closure of ANIMA, the network is now composed of 29 countries (compared to around 20 at the end of Xnoise_EV project in 2016) for which a National Focal Point (NFP) is identified. The figure below shows the European maps with the 29 NFPs active at the end of 2021.

The list of the NFPs with contact information is given in appendix 1.

The role of NFP is expected to evaluate each country's specificity relative to the issues of reducing aviation noise and identify existing actions on mitigation of impact around airports. In the frame of the WP6.2.3, NFPs were required to provide a comprehensive vision of national efforts by identifying relevant programs and research actions dealing with the aviation noise impact.

During the yearly NFPs full meeting, each country was invited to present the National Efforts. The detail of the four-year agenda was as follows.

- 2018 Amsterdam: Bulgaria, Hungary, Netherlands, Romania & Balkan countries
- 2019 Roma: Germany, Italy, Ukraine, United Kingdom, Serbia, Switzerland
- 2020 (Virtual): Belgium, France, Ireland, Slovenia, Spain
- 2021 Brussels: Albania, Czech Republic, Poland, Portugal, Sweden

3 National Efforts Database

The NFPs have been required, during ANIMA project, to collect at the national level the “Efforts” in terms of scientific and technologic actions dealing with the aviation noise reduction.

Each year, from 2018 to 2021, several countries have presented the research actions, the national projects and the national partners involved.

This database is often presented using a template based on a quad-chart form in two pages making it easier to read and use the information. The agenda of the presentations is presented in the previous section.

The list of the National Efforts provided by each NFP is given in appendix 2.

4 Link to the ANIMA Roadmaps

The ANIMA roadmaps are structured in Subset/topics/Subtopics and are described in details in D6.13 document. For each roadmaps topic, the National Efforts are gathered in a large table, country by country.

For each roadmap topic, the country having identified, at least, one National Effort is especially inventoried. The slide number addressing the topic in the NFP presentation is marked. All the countries are pointed out for the roadmap topics concerned.

These links between the national efforts and the ANIMA roadmaps will be very useful for identifying skills and potential partners in the field of reducing aircraft noise and associated annoyance.

The table Roadmaps/National Efforts/Country is given in appendix 3.

5 Conclusions

Thanks to ANIMA project and the NFPs, the historic Xnoise network has been extended to new countries. 29 NFPs are now identified and they were very active during the ANIMA project, attending face-to-face meeting or participating to visioconference. ANIMA has contributed to consolidate the European aviation noise experts network. The WP6 leader and the associated tasks leaders are very grateful to the fruitful business done by all the NFPs.

A large database has been collected and provides a comprehensive vision of national efforts by identifying projects and research actions dealing with the aviation noise impact.

A link with the ANIMA roadmaps has been established making easier the using of this very fruitful database loaded on the ANIMA public website.

APPENDIX 1 - List of National Focal Points (29 NFP)

Albanie

Elona Caushi Tirana airport
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Belgium

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APPENDIX 2 - National Efforts

List of National Projects or Actions in Europe 2018-2021

ALBANIA

- Permanent monitoring upgrade and update of noise contours in frame of airport master plan 2020-2025
- Green Lungs for our cities
- Strengthening Key aerospace technology for smart transport monitoring systems

BELGIUM

- No national research projects dedicated to aviation noise in Belgium
- National Action: Sustain and extend the network

BULGARIA

- Monitoring of aircraft noise in airports
- Standard Method of Computation Noise Contours around airports

CZECH REPUBLIC

- Research Collaboration Agreement GEAC – CTU-FME intensive joint experiments on GE Catalyst turboprop engines

FRANCE

- MAMIES Microphones arrays
- Jet-airframe interaction (Wavepacket-based modelling)
- ARENA New Engine Architectures
- Ambrosia Jet noise (measurements and modelling)
- IJES Installed Jet Effect Simulator
- UAVs Rotor Noise
- Deep Learning for fast predictions of acoustic wave propagation
- ALBUMS Lattice Boltzmann Methods (Aero-Acou & heat transfert)
- OMEGA3 Lattice Boltzmann Methods (Aero-Acou)
- DEBATS Discussion on the health effects of aircraft noise
- ADOPSYS Aeroacoustics of Ducted and Open-rotor Propulsion System
- MACIA Innovative Acoustical Materials for Aeronautics
- ARENA Aeroacoustics of new engine architectures in aeronautics
- CIGALE Conciliation of airport annoyance studies in laboratory and field studies
- BANG Sonic Boom
- DOCCLA Optimisation process for (innovative) acoustic liner design
- SIGMA Core Noise, Modelling of combustion instabilities
- ICI Indirect combustion Noise
- OneLaBZ & CHAMELEON & CLIMB Development in LBM
- MONALISA Improvement of BEMUSE the Onera BEM solver, sound scattering
- SWAHILI Aiframe noise, High Lift Device, numerical predictions
- IDEE Jet Noise, sources identifications in large scale
- HiLiNO High Lift Noise, High quality of experimental data base
- OTTAWAN Distributed Hybrid-Electric Propulsion demonstrator
- AMADEUS Prediction of jet installation noise (coop. TsAGI)

- ECHO development of duct modes detection methods (coop. TsAGI)
- eVTOL Propeller blade design for Urban Air Mobility rotorcraft

GERMANY

- MAMUT Sound source localization in indoor test stands for engines
- LAKS Investigation of Flexible Walls for Acoustic Liners
- AGATA Acoustic effects caused at the fan by BLI
- TOMLIM Optical measurement techniques to determine both the sound pressure and the particle velocity near lined surfaces

HUNGARY

- Network: Maintaining and developing national network
- Committee on Sustainable Development (initialized by the Government) on Airport Noise Pollution. Action stopped.
- Communication with Budapest Airport

IRELAND

- SeMSA: a compact super absorber optimised for broadband, low-frequency noise attenuation.
- Soft Negative bulk modulus sound absorber
- Dark Metamaterials as an aeroengine liner

ITALY

- Installation effects of compressible subsonic jets
- Noise generated by installed propellers
- Under-expanded jets interacting with rigid surfaces
- Multidisciplinary modelling of next-generation aeroengines including technological and operational uncertainties
- Reduced order models for computational aeroacoustics
- Discontinuous Galerkin methods for the linearized Euler/Navier-Stokes equations
- Trailing-edge noise modelling
- Turbomachinery noise radiation
- Acoustic Simulation Tool Enhanced. Open source project.
- FRIDA-Enhanced(FRamework for Integrated Design of Aircraft)
- Adaptive stochastic metamodels for Aeroacoustics
- Acoustic Analogy-based Formulations for Aero/Hydro-acoustic Analysis of Rotary Wing Devices
- Development of boundary-field formulations for the analysis of sound scattered by moving bodies
- Aeroacoustics of small propeller
- Network: Improve the coordination of the aeroacoustic community at National level.

NETHERLANDS

- Noise Synthesis and Auralisation
- Noise shielding assessment of current and novel aircraft configurations
- Analysis of landing gear noise
- Sound field calculation and sound sources identification of rotating sources in a moving medium

PORTUGAL

- The effect of shear and bias flows on the performance of acoustic liners;
- Acoustic-entropy waves in a flow with temperature gradients and heat exchanges
- Acoustic-vortical-entropy waves in a nozzle flow with heat exchanges and uniform swirl
- Acoustic-vortical waves in a nozzle with non-uniform swirl and adiabatic flow
- Extension of the Lighthill's acoustic analogy to vortical and non-isentropic flow
- Shielding of noise from a source near an aft fuselage tail cone
- Sound interference due to multipath effects caused by reflections from buildings
- Low-noise aircraft design and configurations
- Optimization of non-uniform acoustic liners
- Noise shielding by a S-shaped inlet or nozzle
- Sound propagation in a curved inlet or nozzle
- Acoustic matching of straight, curved and twisted ducts

ROMANIA & BALKANS

- Jet engine test rig silencer
- Acoustic metamaterials for aeroengine applications
- Network: Communication with Balkan specialists

SLOVENIA

- No national research projects or programs dedicated to aviation noise

SPAIN

- Noise monitoring accredited according to ISO 20906
- Bio-inspired acoustic materials

SWEDEN

- EleFanT–Electric Fan Thruster: Multi-disciplinary design of an electrically powered thruster
- CIDER-Correlation and physIcs based preDictionof noisE scenaRios

SWITZERLAND

- IDeAL: Impact Driven Assessment of novel Low-noise aircraft concepts
- sonAIR : Validation of the aircraft noise simulation model. Estimation of flight parameters based on radar data. Development and operation of a monitoring system for aircraft noise for the specific demands
- Listening tests to assess the annoyance of helicopter noise compared to wing-mounted propeller driven aircraft
- LNAS: Implementation of a pilot assisting system for low noise landing procedures at Zurich Airport
- SiRENE: Short and Long Term Effects of Transportation Noise Exposure

UNITED KINGDOM

- ACCLAIM. Airport Capacity Consequences Leveraging Aviation Integrated Modelling
- ANCO: Aircraft Noise and Cardiovascular Outcomes
- Understanding and developing new noise reduction mechanism for aerofoils in unsteady flow through the use of analytical mathematics
- JINA. Jet Installation Noise Abatement
- Effect of Separation and Stall on Aerofoil Noise
- ACAPELLA. Assessment Capability for Advanced Predictions of Engine Level Acoustics

UKRAINE

- Aircraft take-off and landing noise measurement
- Flight path for arrival studies and modeling for lateral attenuation effect
- Assessing the impact of aircraft noise near an airport
- Model for interference of direct and reflected sound waves
- Method for determining the acoustic power of the UAV
- Acoustic localization of UAV

APPENDIX 3 - National Efforts linked to the ANIMA Roadmaps

For each roadmap topic, the country having identified, at least, one National Effort is inventoried. The slide number addressing the topic in the NFP presentation is marked. All the countries are pointed out for the roadmap topics concerned.

The following 24 roadmap topics are associated to the countries having a contribution in aviation noise reduction. The link is referenced using the number of the slide in the PDF file or the number of the project if any (P).

For example, Italy has a national research or action in first the topic below, the slide dedicated to this action and included in the PDF file is slide number 7 (S7).

Aero-acoustic integration of UHBR turbofan propulsion system

Italy: S7

UK: S16, S17

Low noise airframe noise design

Spain: P2

Operational noise abatement

Switzerland: S6

Noise source level

France: S13, S58

Italy: S17

Aircraft level

Ukraine: S36, S39

Trajectory impact on noise

Ukraine: S19, S32

High fidelity methods: Turbulence

France: S8, S17, S18, S46 S54

Italy: S4, S6

Portugal: P4

Ukraine: S14

High fidelity methods: Noise generation

France: S17, S18, S21, S25, S34, S36, S38, S40, S42, S50

Italy: S15

Netherlands: P3

Portugal: P2, P3

Ukraine: S14, S18

High fidelity methods: Noise propagation & radiation

France: S5, S15, S16, S17, S18, S23, S32, S38, S40, S42, S44

Germany: S2, S3

Ireland: P1, P2, P3

Italy: S9, S11, S13

Netherlands: P4

Portugal: P1, P2, P4, P5

Romania: P2

Spain: P2

Ukraine: S22, S23

Integrated methods for prediction and design optimisation

France: S59

Italy: S7, S10

Switzerland: P1, P2, P3, P4

Ukraine: S22

High fidelity methods: New architecture

France: S9, S11, S21, S25, S44, S52

Germany: S5

Netherlands: P2

Portugal: P6, P7, P8

Switzerland: P1

Experimental techniques: Velocity

Germany: S6

Experimental techniques: Pressure

Germany: S6

Experimental techniques: Acoustics

Albania: P2

France: S7, S12, S48, S56

Germany: S2

Romania: P1

Airport response

Albania: P1

Bulgaria:

Hungary: S4

Poland: S4

Spain: P1

Switzerland: P4

UK: S10

Ukraine: S33

Annoyance models

France: S28

Switzerland: P1, P5

Health Models

France: S19

Switzerland: P5 (S10)

UK: S12

Qualified balanced scorecard

Switzerland: P5 (S10)

Ukraine: S35

Noise exposure models

Switzerland: P3

Impact models

Spain: P1

Audiovisual simulations

Netherlands: P1

Interdependencies

Albania: P2

Metrics

Albania: P2

Poland: S18

Switzerland: P5

Supersonic aircraft low boom design

France: S30

